

370 cm^{-1} shifted to lower frequency range 3 350–330 cm^{-1} suggesting rupture of hydrogen bonding and participation of the phenolic OH in coordination. The ligand band around 2 580–570 cm^{-1} disappears suggesting coordination through the carboxylate group. The $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ moves from 1 610 to 1 580 and from 1 605 to 1 580 cm^{-1} in the H_2NP and H_2SI complexes, respectively, indicating involvement of azomethine nitrogen in coordination. The complexes also showed bands in the region 1 570–1 560 cm^{-1} due to ν_{as} (COO). The appearance of bands in the narrow ranges 415–400 and 522–500 cm^{-1} suggests metal–nitrogen and metal–oxygen bondings⁶ in the complexes. Thus the ligands offered tridentate (O, N, O), chelation to the lanthanide ions to form octahedral complexes.

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Studies on Complexes of Tridentate Schiff Bases derived from 8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and Diamines with Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II)

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COUMARIN and its derivatives have been found to exhibit physiological activity and are also extensively used as analytical reagents¹⁻⁴. 7-Hydroxycoumarin known for its antibiotic and antifungal activities^{5,6} having substituents like amino and nitro at position-8 and methyl at position-4, has been investigated for complexing ability^{7,8}. 8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin has been found to exhibit anticoagulant and plant growth regulant property^{9,10}. The present paper deals with the synthesis and characterisation of title metal ions

complexes of Schiff bases derived from 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl coumarin and ethylenediamine/propylenediamine.

Experimental

8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (AHC) was prepared¹¹ and the other reagents were of A.R. grade. Ethylenediamine (en) and propylenediamine were purified by distillation under reduced pressure. The Schiff bases, *N*-(8-aceto-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin)ethylenediamine (AHCE) (m.p. 131.5°) and *N*-(8-aceto-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin)propylenediamine (AHCP) (m.p. 146°) were synthesised by refluxing (30 min) AHC and ethylenediamine/propylenediamine in 1 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol. On cooling, yellow crystalline products were obtained which were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Complexes were prepared by mixing ethanolic solutions of ligands and metal chlorides in 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 molar ratios. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 1–3 h and then concentrated. On cooling, the complexes were filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried in air.

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents of the ligands and the complexes were estimated by microanalysis. The metal estimations were carried out following standard procedures¹². Magnetic and spectral studies were made as reported earlier¹³. The analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The molar conductance of the complexes was measured in DMF ($10^{-3}M$) using a Elico CM-82 conductivity bridge with a cell having cell constant of 1.0 cm^{-1} . The molar conductance values of all Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes were in the range 4–13.6 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ indicating that the complexes are non-electrolytes¹⁴.

Copper(II) complexes: The room temperature μ_{eff} values of Cu^{II} complexes are close to the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M. and indicate the presence of one unpaired electron. The electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complexes show bands in the regions 18 500–19 000, 21 500–22 000 and 24 000–25 000 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the transitions ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$ and ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$, respectively assuming a square-planar geometry. The appearance of third band may be attributed to the charge transfer transition.

Nickel(II) complexes: In the electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes, three distinct bands appear in the range 10 025–10 660 (ν_1), 16 390–17 950 (ν_2) and 27 025–28 830 cm^{-1} (ν_3), respectively. The latter two bands are characteristics of an octahedral complex¹⁵ which is further confirmed by the ν_2/ν_1 ratio (1.6–1.8).

Cobalt(II) complexes: The magnetic moment values for Co^{II} complexes are in the ranges expected

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		AM Ω^{-1} cm ² mol ⁻¹	μ_{eff} B.M.
				N	Metal		
1.	[Cu(C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂)Cl] ^a	Brown	176	7.65 (7.82)	17.50 (17.74)	13.6	1.70
2.	[Ni(C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂) ₂]	Yellowish green	198°	9.50 (9.71)	10.02 (10.17)	6.7	3.0
3.	[Co(C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂) ₂]	Yellowish brown	200°	9.51 (9.71)	10.03 (10.20)	4.0	4.82
4.	[Cu(C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂)Cl] ^b	Light brown	181	7.33 (7.52)	17.00 (17.07)	13.1	1.8
5.	[Ni(C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂) ₂]	Yellowish green	205°	9.04 (9.26)	9.54 (9.70)	5.1	3.12
6.	[Co(C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂) ₂]	Dark brown	209°	9.04 (9.26)	9.61 (9.70)	5.2	4.70

^a Cl % : 9.80 (9.91). ^b Cl % : 9.31 (9.54). ° Decomposed.

for octahedral geometry¹⁶. In the electronic spectra of these complexes, two bands are mainly observed at ~9 000 and ~24 000 cm⁻¹, assigned to ν_1 and ν_3 transitions, respectively, considering a O_h symmetry. Two shoulders ⁴T_{1g}(F)→²T_{1g}, ²T_{2g} (~18 000 cm⁻¹) and ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴A_{2g}(F) (~19 000 cm⁻¹) may be considered either due to the splitting of ν_3 , in many components or they may be because of appearance of ν_2 transitions¹⁷. The ratio of ν_2/ν_1 (1.95–2.2) suggests the shoulders ~19 000 cm⁻¹ as ν_2 transitions for these complexes.

In ligands, AHCE and AHCP, the band around 1 620 cm⁻¹ is assigned¹⁹ to $\nu_{C=N}$ (azomethine) vibrations. The ligands with one primary amino group is expected to show two bands in the region 3 100–3 400 cm⁻¹ due $\nu_S(NH_2)$ and $\nu_{as}(NH_2)$ vibrations²⁰. The presence of a phenolic group in such compounds makes it difficult to differentiate between ν_{NH_2} and ν_{OH} vibrations since both absorb around the same frequencies. Thus, a band around 3 200 cm⁻¹ has been attributed to a combination of $\nu_{NH_2} + \nu_{OH}$ vibrations. In the complexes, the $\nu_{C=N}$, $\nu_{NH_2} + \nu_{OH}$ vibrations have undergone a negative shift by 50–75 cm⁻¹, indicating the coordination of the azomethine, primary amino and phenolic OH groups of the ligands. This view is further supported by the appearance of bands corresponding to ν_{M-N} (525–550) and ν_{M-O} (450–470 cm⁻¹). In the complex nos. 1 and 4 (Table 1), metal halogen bands are also present as indicated by the appearance of bands²¹, ν_{M-Cl} (340–370 cm⁻¹).

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Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Dioxouranium(II) with Thiophene-2-aldehydethiosemicarbazone

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METAL complexes of thiosemicarbazides have been known for their pharmacological applications¹. Significant antitubercular², fungicidal³ and antiviral⁴ activities have been reported for thiosemicarbazides and their derivatives. Extensive studies on the investigation of metal complexes of thiosemicarbazones have been undertaken in recent years. The present study describes the synthesis and